

Solar-powered GPS Guided Water Body Cleaning Bot

Gayitri H M¹

Ranjitha R²

Saniha H N³

Surabhi M P⁴

Pranjal Singh⁵

Department of Electronics and Communication, JSS Science and Technology University, Mysuru, India¹⁻⁵

Abstract— The importance of maintaining clean water sources for all living beings cannot be overstated, yet water pollution persists due to various sources such as industrial waste, garbage, and sewage. Traditional methods for cleaning water bodies like lakes and ponds are often insufficient. To address this pressing issue, we propose a technological solution designed to efficiently and effectively clean polluted water bodies. This project focuses on developing a robotic system capable of autonomously collecting floating waste from water surfaces. The core of our robotic system is built around an Arduino Uno microcontroller, which serves as the central processing unit. A DC-DC buck converter is integrated to manage power supply efficiently, stepping down the voltage for different components. Motors controlled via a motor driver handle propulsion and steering, ensuring smooth movement across the water. A Bluetooth module allows for wireless communication and remote control, enabling user interaction for updates or manual override. The system uses a Neo 7M GPS module with an integrated compass for precise navigation, allowing the robot to follow predetermined paths or adapt in real-time to cover targeted areas. The waste collection mechanism is robust and efficient, capable of handling various types of floating debris. The collected waste is stored in an easily removable compartment, ensuring efficient disposal and minimal downtime. By combining innovative engineering with environmental consciousness, our project contributes to combating water pollution, safeguarding ecosystems, and supporting communities reliant on clean water sources through an autonomous, GPS-guided robotic system equipped with advanced sensors and waste collection capabilities.

Keywords— Robotic cleaning, Autonomous navigation, GPS guidance, floating waste collection, water pollution.

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of plastic pollution in water bodies poses a significant threat to environmental sustainability and public health. With modern lifestyles increasingly reliant on disposable plastics, the accumulation of waste in aquatic ecosystems has become a pressing concern worldwide[1]. Traditional methods of cleaning water bodies, such as manual labor and mechanical filtration systems, are often labor-intensive, time-consuming, and insufficient to cope with the escalating levels of pollution. These methods are hindered by their limited capacity to cover large areas efficiently and their dependence on human intervention, which can be costly and impractical for continuous maintenance.

In response to this challenge, the development of innovative technological solutions is imperative. This paper introduces a pioneering approach to address plastic pollution in water bodies through the design and implementation of a fully autonomous robotic system. By leveraging advanced technologies such as GPS navigation and autonomous operation, the proposed robotic solution aims to revolutionize the process of cleaning water parks and bodies, offering a sustainable and efficient alternative to conventional methods[3]. The autonomous nature of the robotic system enables it to operate continuously without the need for human supervision, thereby reducing labor costs and increasing efficiency.

The robotic system is equipped with a GPS module to determine its precise location and navigate predefined paths within the water body. This enables the robot to cover the entire area systematically, ensuring comprehensive cleaning of the water park or body[8]. Additionally, the robot is fitted with a durable fabric net that spans the entire area, effectively capturing floating waste such as bottles, plastic covers, and other debris. The net is designed to be easily replaceable or cleaned as needed, further enhancing the system's efficiency and sustainability. Overall, the implementation of this autonomous robotic solution offers a promising strategy for mitigating plastic pollution in water bodies, safeguarding ecosystems, and promoting public health and well-being.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

The issue of water logging due to plastic, thermocole and metal is prompting both development and it favors ailments like intestinal sickness, typhoid and so on. Cleaning the wastes by utilizing manual procedures would be insufficient as it regularly covers immense territory of works and endeavors with plausibility to getting influenced by different sicknesses from the irresistible microorganisms present in the sewage while cleaning manually. This study features a proposed plan of garbage gathering system viable and effective for tidying up waste from rivers, channels and lakes. The trash gathering system is explicitly coordinated to application for getting up a wide assortment of debris, including gliding litter, trash, logs, disposed tires and others. The integrated system incorporates the usage of IoT technology that has the ability to monitor and control the entire process. From the interest and need of cleaning contaminations in the conduits territory, the vessel has been created to suit the prerequisite of working at places other than seaward zone, giving more decisions for the utilization of cleaning garbage and waste from the water environment.[1]

This paper describes the design and construction of an automated water surface cleaner. It is executed thinking of the present situation of our national rivers consisting of millions of wastes, hydrophytes, toxicant plastics, polythene, dead leaves etc. The use of an automated water surface cleaner reduces water pollution at 10% of the total water pollution. Also, it is used in those places where people cannot reach easily. The main focus of this paper is to eliminate trashes off the water surface by a remote control system, thus reducing human effort. It requires RF remote connection for navigation purposes, which is the input for wheel motors and a conveyor belt, a GSM to get notified when the device is significantly loaded, a motor connected conveyor belt to collect trashes and an ARDUINO acting as the interface in between. A bin is attached to gather trashes and a sensor to notify the user if it is full. This system is economical as well since it reduces the labor cost required to do all these kinds of stuff.[2]

Ephemeris parameters in navigation message data which are updated every 2 hours has irregular patterns, But in this works, we discovered regular patterns in 24h interval some ephemeris parameters (Semi-Major Axis, Eccentricity, Mean Motion, Inclination Angle, Rate of Inclination Angle, Harmonic Perturbation Terms). In this paper, we evaluate the ephemeris parameter estimation algorithms for SA-GPS using 24h interval GPS ephemeris patterns. Using 24 hours ephemeris parameter regular patterns, we propose simple estimation methods (Polynomial method, Sine estimation method) for estimation of current ephemeris parameters.[3]

This paper presents the design of a cost-effective remote controlled floating waste removing robot which can be used in canals, ponds, rivers or in oceans. As the usage of plastic is growing in an unregulated way in many countries, toxins from these elements cause an imbalance in the ecosystem and are threatening to human health leading to cancers, birth defects and immune system problems. A prototype of the robot is built in which there are two propellers which are connected with two DC motors to move forward, backward, left and right- mobile application-based Bluetooth control system to control the robot from a distance and a robotic hand to make it easy to collect the trashes. A conveyor belt arrangement guiding the trash to the collection box and a sensor arrangement for protection against overloading have been used. Both manufacturing and maintenance cost are kept very affordable. The prototype itself can collect trash weighing upto 10 kg, clean an area of about 3000 square centimeters drawing only 45 watts from the battery. The robot has the capability of working for four hours continuously without the necessity of charging. Floating waste collecting robot can be a saviour for the endangered aquatic animals.[4]

It is very dreadful that huge liters of excrement are being deposited into the rivers across our country. The pollutants and toxins are assisting the amassing of the toxicant in water thus affecting aquatic life. Only when the detritus floating above the water bodies become persistent, the governments' plan of action is set about and unfortunately by that time, the life cycle in that water body breaks. This research work focuses on deploying a solution for the unfavorable effects on the floating refuse, and henceforth reduces the pollution caused due to the unsettled wastes including plastics and plant weeds. The project aims to develop a waste collecting boat to scavenge the water body and abolish the floating waste. This is done by employing a conveyor belt connected to the front line of the boat. Boat movement is established using a remote control application by incorporating an RF module along with an encoder-decoder pair. This method will reduce the cost of operation because of less human involvement and labour. Major challenges in implementing the boat are compact mechanical design and reliable power supply. The principle feature of this boat is the collection of refuse and floating weeds from the surface of the water into a basket which is removable.[5]

70% of the fresh water in liquid form of our country is converted into being unfit for consumption. Not only India, but other countries are also suffering from the same problem. This has been explained clearly by the help of considerable number of references in this paper. Various sources of pollution such as sewage discharge, industrial effluents and agricultural runoff and their potential has been studied in mass. Various prescribed standards for different category of inland water have been explained. The paper also consists of the potential and extent of various components which pollute the water. Finally, effect of water pollution has been shown in nutshell.[6]

This paper explains India is holey country. There is lots of water pollution of Godavari River at Nashik. The water pollution is very important problem in rivers, ponds and water bodies near Godavari River at Nashik. Due to increase in water pollution in the form to waste debris; it is hampering the life of aquatic animal and make their life in danger. Similarly sometimes the aquatic animal tends to eats surface waste debris considering it as a food; which ultimately cause the death of animals. Due to polluted water is are

many skin diseases to human kind are observed. So that to reduce the water pollution we are trying to make pond cleaning robot. "Pond Cleaning Robot" a device which involves the removing the waste debris from water surface and safely dispose from the water body. The pond cleaning robot works on Bluetooth to extract waste water debris, plastics garbage from Godavari River at Nashik.[7]

Increasing commercial use of the Global Positioning System will soon make it possible to locate anything, anywhere, anytime. The Global Positioning System can provide extremely accurate location information for mobile objects and people which is far superior to earlier tracking techniques. The challenge today is integrating the necessary components into older systems and improving GPS accuracy in areas with numerous obstructions. As more devices become GPS enabled, accuracy will increase and the system's scale and global reach will benefit everyone. Wireless technology promises to be a key element in any long-term solution.[8]

The litters of sewage, industries and other sources are being dumped in our rivers day by day. Like other countries' the government of India has also taken many initiatives like "Namomi Gange", "Narmada Bachao" and so many initiatives to make the rivers clean. Keeping this in mind, the project work is implemented to collect and discharge floating litters from the rivers or any other water bodies featuring the image process in the camera module and controlled through GPS module. The implemented robot is small, lightweight, floating, energy efficient, environmentally compatible (in shape, size, colour, materials and energy supply) and is able to navigate autonomously and in coordination with each other, in a variety of scenarios, such as coastal waters, artificial and natural lakes, lagoons and rivers.[9]

In order to replace the traditional manual cleaning rivers and lakes water hyacinth, garbage and so on, and then improve the clean-up efficiency, while addressing the labor force of large salvage, low security issues, a new amphibious cleaning robot is developed. The robot is mainly composed of solar automatic tracking system, amphibious amphibious system, rotary gather system, rotary collection system and so on. Its structure is simple, safe and reliable, and it takes solar energy as the main source of energy. It can be widely used in rivers, rivers and lakes water hyacinth, garbage salvage operations. The machine has the advantages of high degree of automation, simple operation, safe and efficient.[10]

III. METHODOLOGY

The materials, procedures, tools and data bases utilized:

- **Arduino Uno:** Serves as the central microcontroller, managing all operations. It processes data from sensors, controls the motors via the motor driver, and handles communication with other components like the GPS, compass, and Bluetooth module, ensuring coordinated functioning of the bot.
- **Neo 7M GPS Module with Compass:** Provides precise real-time location (latitude and longitude) and orientation (heading) data, essential for navigation. This allows the bot to determine its current position and adjust its course to follow a predefined path or reach specific targets in the river.
- **Motor Driver (L298N):** Acts as an intermediary between the Arduino and the motors. It allows the Arduino to control motor speed and direction by sending appropriate signals, enabling the bot to maneuver accurately and efficiently in the water.
- **DC Motors:** Propel the bot through the water. Controlled by the motor driver, they adjust their speed and direction based on commands from the Arduino, allowing the bot to navigate toward desired locations or follow specific routes.
- **Bluetooth Module:** Enables wireless communication with the bot. Users can set operational parameters, control the bot remotely, and receive real-time updates on its status, enhancing flexibility and ease of operation without needing direct physical access.
- **Solar Panels:** Capture sunlight and convert it into electrical energy. This energy powers the bot and charges its batteries, ensuring sustainable, continuous operation by harnessing renewable energy, which is particularly useful in remote or extended missions.
- **DC-DC Buck Converter:** Steps down the higher voltage from the solar panels to a lower, regulated voltage suitable for charging the batteries and powering the electronic components. This ensures safe and efficient power management within the bot's system.
- **PVC Pipes:** Form the structural framework of the bot, providing buoyancy and stability. These pipes are lightweight yet durable, ensuring the bot remains afloat and stable while navigating through various water conditions, protecting internal components from water damage.

- **Arduino IDE:** The Arduino Integrated Development Environment (IDE) for writing, compiling, and uploading firmware code to the Arduino microcontroller, implementing navigation algorithms and control logic.
- **GPS Library:** A GPS library compatible with the chosen GPS module, allowing the Arduino to communicate with the GPS module and parse GPS data for navigation purposes.
- **Compass Library:** A compass library compatible with the chosen compass module, providing functions for reading compass data and calculating heading angles for navigation.
- **Motor Control Library:** A motor control library or custom motor control code to interface with motor drivers and control the speed and direction of DC motors for propulsion.

Fig.1: Block diagram of proposed model

A. Requirement Analysis:

The project's specifications and objectives are delineated based on the critical needs for river cleaning and emergency rescue operations. This involves a comprehensive assessment of the challenges posed by pollution and potential emergencies in river environments. Through stakeholder consultation and environmental studies, the project aims to define clear goals for the robotic system, including efficient debris collection, autonomous navigation, and swift emergency response capabilities. Research is conducted to meticulously select hardware components that meet stringent criteria for reliability, compatibility with the chosen platform (such as Arduino microcontrollers), and suitability for operation in aquatic environments. Factors such as waterproofing, durability, and sensor precision are prioritized in the component selection process.

B. Hardware Assembly:

Once the specifications are finalized, the identified hardware components are procured, ensuring they align with the project requirements. These components typically include Arduino microcontrollers, GPS modules, compass modules, motors, motor drivers, and various sensors crucial for environmental perception as shown in figure 1. Careful attention is paid to secure connections and proper mounting to fortify the robotic platform against water exposure and mechanical stress.

C. Software Development:

Firmware development for the Arduino microcontroller is undertaken to interpret GPS data, calculate navigation paths, and control motor movements based on sensor inputs. Algorithms for autonomous navigation, obstacle avoidance, and emergency response behaviours are devised and implemented. A user interface is designed to facilitate remote monitoring and control of the robot's operation, empowering operators to oversee missions and intervene if necessary.

D. Testing and Calibration:

Initial testing of individual hardware components is conducted to validate functionality and detect any defects or compatibility issues. Following this, hardware and software components are integrated to create a complete robotic system, and

system-level testing ensues to validate overall functionality. Calibration of sensors, fine-tuning of navigation algorithms, and optimization of power management settings are undertaken to enhance performance and efficiency.

E. Simulation and Virtual Testing:

Simulation software is leveraged to emulate various environmental conditions and mission scenarios, enabling virtual testing of the robot's navigation and response capabilities. Results from simulations are validated against real-world data, and algorithms are refined iteratively to improve accuracy and reliability.

F. Field Testing:

Controlled field deployments, such as in pools or small rivers, are conducted to assess the robot's performance in real-world conditions. Evaluation includes autonomous navigation, debris collection, and response to simulated emergency situations. Observations are meticulously documented, and areas for improvement are identified.

By following this methodology, we aim to systematically develop, test, and validate a GPS-guided river cleaning and emergency rescue robot that meets the project objectives and demonstrates practical utility in addressing real-world challenges.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The solar-powered GPS-guided river cleaning bot employs an Arduino Uno microcontroller as its central processing unit, orchestrating the coordination between various components. This includes interfacing as shown in figure 2, with a Neo 7M GPS module, which, in conjunction with an integrated compass, provides the bot with real-time location and orientation data. This data is essential for navigating the river and ensuring the bot remains on its predetermined course. The bot harnesses solar energy through its onboard solar panels. These panels convert sunlight into electrical power, which is then regulated by a DC-DC buck converter. The converter steps down the voltage from the solar panels to a level appropriate for charging the onboard batteries and powering the electronic components. This system ensures that the bot operates sustainably, relying on renewable energy sources to maintain its functionality. For propulsion, the bot is equipped with motors controlled by an L298N motor driver. The Arduino sends signals to the motor driver, which in turn adjusts the speed and direction of the motors. This setup allows the bot to move precisely according to the GPS coordinates and compass readings, effectively navigating towards user-specified targets. These targets and other operational parameters are input by users via a Bluetooth module, which provides a convenient wireless communication interface. To ensure precise movement, calibration parameters are set within the Arduino's programming. These parameters account for factors such as motor response time and environmental conditions, optimizing the bot's navigation accuracy.

Fig.2: Hardware implementation of proposed model

As the bot traverses the river, it is outfitted with nets or other collection mechanisms to gather floating debris. This design ensures that the bot can autonomously clean the river surface, collecting trash and other pollutants. The collected debris can be easily removed during routine maintenance. Continuous solar charging is a key feature of the bot, allowing it to operate for extended periods without the need for manual recharging. This makes it particularly effective for use in remote or large river systems where constant human oversight is impractical. Overall, the integration of GPS navigation, solar power, and autonomous debris collection enables the bot to perform its cleaning duties efficiently and sustainably, contributing to cleaner river environments.

The calibration process is essential for precise movement and involves rotating the bot in various directions to determine offsets and calibration errors for the x, y, and z axes. These values are crucial for the accurate functioning of the GPS and compass, ensuring the bot can navigate with precision. Once calibration is complete, users can enter latitude and longitude coordinates via a Bluetooth communication app, such as Serial Bluetooth shown in figure 3. These coordinates can be input either as a series of

waypoints or a single endpoint, defining the bot's navigation path along the river. With the coordinates set, the Arduino processes this data and controls the motors accordingly, adjusting the bot's wheels to move in the specified direction. As the bot navigates along the designated path, it utilizes attached nets or collection mechanisms to gather floating waste effectively. This autonomous navigation allows the bot to clean the river efficiently, following user-defined routes and continuously collecting debris. The integration of GPS-guided movement and waste collection mechanisms ensures that the bot can maintain a clean river environment while operating independently of human intervention.

```
Terminal
16-30-20.999 xoff: 53
16-30-20.999 yoff: 512
16-30-20.999 zoff: 201
16-30-20.999 heading: 63.43
16-30-20.999 .....
16-30-22.498 xoff: 53
16-30-22.498 yoff: 512
16-30-22.498 zoff: 201
16-30-22.498 heading: 61.63
16-30-22.498 ..... Initialize HMC5883L
16-30-24.497 1
16-30-24.497 2
16-30-24.497 3
16-30-24.497 press 1 to calibrae , press 2 if done
16-30-35.777 2
16-30-37.194 enter xoffset
16-30-52.576 53
16-30-54.221 enter yoffset
16-3104.852 512
16-3106.246 enter zoffset
16-3113.920 201
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.28
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.52
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.28
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.52
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.45
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.81
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 281.00
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 281.40
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.58
16-3116.326 heading
16-3116.326 280.64
16-3116.326 enter calib Error
```

Fig.3: Entering offset values in the app

The project successfully developed a solar-powered river cleaning robot guided by GPS. Using Arduino Uno, GPS module, and compass, it navigates towards specified coordinates, collecting floating waste along the river's path. Calibration ensures precise movement, while continuous solar charging enables sustainable operation.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of a GPS-guided river cleaning and emergency rescue robot involves careful consideration of hardware and software requirements to ensure the system's functionality, reliability, and effectiveness. By integrating essential components such as Arduino microcontroller, GPS module, compass module, motors, sensors, and appropriate software libraries, the robot can navigate autonomously, collect debris, and respond to emergency situations in waterways with precision and efficiency.

The hardware requirements encompass components for navigation, propulsion, sensing, and power supply, while the software requirements include firmware for control algorithms, libraries for sensor interfacing, and potentially a user interface for remote operation and monitoring. By fulfilling these requirements and implementing robust hardware and software solutions, the robot can fulfill its objectives of enhancing river cleaning efforts, mitigating environmental pollution, and aiding in emergency response operations, contributing to the preservation and sustainability of aquatic ecosystems and the safety of communities residing near water bodies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We express our sincere gratitude to our institution SJCE JSS Science and Technology University, Dr U B Mahadevaswamy, HOD Dept. of ECE, guide Dr. Gayitri H M, Associate Professor, Dept. of ECE, project panel members and our families for being a constant source of support, and guidance without which this project would not have been successful.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. N. Mohammed, S. Al-Zubaidi, Siti Humairah Kamarul Bahrain, "Design and Development of River Cleaning Robot Using IoT Technology", Published by IEEE, in 2020 16th IEEE International Colloquium on Signal Processing & Its Applications (CSPA).
- [2] Md. Raseduzzaman Ruman; Mukta Das; S.M. Istiaque Mahmud; Shantanu Kumar Nath, "Automated Marine Surface Trash Cleaner", Published by IEEE, in 2019.
- [3] Jongsun Ahn, Ha Yeong Song, Sangkyung Sung, Jin-bok Kim, "An efficient GPS parameter prediction method using GPS ephemeris patterns for Self-Assisted GPS", Published by IEEE, in ICCAS 2010.
- [4] Abir Akib, Faiza Tasnim, Disha Biswas, Maeesha Binte Hashem, "Unmanned Floating Waste Collecting Robot", Published by IEEE, in TENCON 2019 - 2019 IEEE Region 10 Conference (TENCON).
- [5] Jishnu Satheesh, Anagha P Nair, Devipriya M., Chithra A., "Wireless Communication based Water Surface Cleaning Boat", Published by IEEE, in 2020 4th International Conference on Trends in Electronics and Informatics (ICOEI).
- [6] Anil K Dwivedi, "Researches In Water Pollution: A Review", Published by International Research Journal of Natural and Applied Sciences.
- [7] Soumya, H.M. Preeti, BaswarajGadgay, "Pond Cleaning Robot", Published by N/A.
- [8] R. Bajaj, S.L. Ranaweera, D.P. Agrawal, "GPS: location-tracking technology", Published by IEEE.
- [9] Bhaskar Banerjee, Kaushik Mukherjee, Piyasa Mukherjee, Shovon Nandi, "The Best Way to Utilize Robotic Trash Boat with GPS Navigation", Published by IEEE.
- [10] Nan Pan, Lifeng Kan, Yajun Sun, Jinlun Dai, "Amphibious clean — Up robot", Published by IEEE.